

Seagrass Bioregional Species Key:

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Tropical Atlantic Bioregion

Species identification key including photo guide, global range maps, drawings, and flowers.

From:

SeagrassNet

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With ratings from:

IUCN Red List of Threatened Species

Seagrass Red List

*Bioregional Guide to the Seagrass Species of the World. 2025. F.T. Short.
Available on-line www.SeagrassNet.org.*

Tt *Thalassia testudinum*

- Key
- Flat leaves with small dark tannin cells
 - Fibrous leaf sheath
 - Rhizome with scale between nodes
 - Leaves 10-60 cm long
 - Dioecious
 - Often with red leaves

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male buds

male female

young fruit

Sf *Syringodium filiforme*

- Key
- Leaves cylindrical
 - Leaf tips taper
 - Leaves 10-60 cm long
 - Dioecious

Flowering Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Male

female

fruits

Hw *Halodule wrightii*

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tip usually 2 points
- Leaves 2-22 cm long
- Rhizome whitish
- Dioecious
- Depth -1 to 20 m
- Sometimes leaves red or black

Flowering Parts

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hv *Halodule beaudettei*

Bioregion
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Samper-Villarreal 2024

- Key
- Leaves flat and thin
 - Leaf tip with 3 points, long central tooth
 - Leaves 15 cm long
 - Dioecious
 - Depth 0 to 10 m

Extinction Risk: Data Deficient

Hd *Halophila decipiens*

Key

- Paddle-shaped leaves
- Leaf hairs on both sides
- Leaf margins serrated
- Leaves 1-4 cm long
- Monoecious
- Depth 0 to 30 m

Flowering Parts

male & female

fruit

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

HI *Halophila baillonii*

Key

- Leaves in rosette on 1-6 cm stem
- 4-5 leaves per rosette
- Leaf margins serrated
- Leaves 2-3 cm long, rounded tip
- Dioecious

Extinction Risk: **Vulnerable**

Flowering Parts

He *Halophila engelmanni*

- Key
- Leaves in rosette on stem
 - 5-8 leaves per rosette
 - Pointed leaves with small petiole
 - Leaves 2-5 cm long
 - Dioecious
 - Depth 0 to 5 m

Extinction Risk: **Near Threatened**

Flowering Parts

Ho *Halophila ovalis*

Bioregion
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Key

- Oval-shaped leaves, 1-4 cm long
- Leaves often red or purple
- No leaf hairs
- Leaf margins smooth
- Depth 0 to 10 m
- Dioecious

Flowering Parts

female

male

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Hs *Halophila stipulacea*

Invasive species

- Elongated paddle-shaped leaves to 6cm
- Leaf stippled and bullate, tip serrated
- Distinctive scales cover the stem
- Depth 0 to 60m
- Dioecious
- Range expanding

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

Flowering Parts

male

female

G Koplovitz

Rm *Ruppia maritima*

Key

- Leaves flat and thin
- Leaf tapers to tip
- Leaves 4-22 cm long
- Depth -1 to 20 m

Extinction Risk: Least Concern

male

Flowering Parts

female

fruit

Global Seagrass Species References

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